

PLEDGE

Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance

D1.1 First Needs Analysis Report

January, 2025

**Funded by
the European Union**

Document details

Project Acronym/ Name:	PLEDGE
Project URL:	www.pledgeproject.eu
Project Type:	HORIZON-RIA
EU CALL:	HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01
Grant Agreement No.:	101132560
Project Start Date:	1 February 2024
Project End Date:	31 January 2027
Project duration:	36 months
Workpackage:	WP1 Comprehensive mapping of existing knowledge
Deliverable:	First Needs Analysis Report
Due date of Deliverable:	30/04/2024
Actual Submission Date:	30/01/2025
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable:	Report Author(s): Gulnaz Sharafutdinova, Iris Magne (Kings College London) Contributors: Ayhan Kaya (İstanbul Bilgi University)
Reviewed by:	Alina Mozolevska (PMBSNU)
Revision:	1.0 (example)
Dissemination Level:	Public

Document History

Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
1.0	7.04.2024	First draft shared for review and comments	Ayhan Kaya (Bilgi)
2.0	15.04.2024	Comments provided to the structure and content	Alina Mozolevska (PMBSNU)
3.0	23.04.2024	Updated version shared and all partners contributed	Gulnaz Sharafutdinova (KCL) , Ayhan Kaya (Bilgi)
4.0	26.04.2024	Final version sent for quality check	Tereza Capelos (University of Southampton), Mikko Salmela (University of Helsinki)
5.0	30.04.2024	Final version submitted	Mikko Salmela (UH)
6.0	28.11.2024	Revised Version that includes the Stakeholders	Gulnaz Sharafutdinova (KCL), Ayhan Kaya (Bilgi)
7.0	02.12.2024	Draft shared for review and comments	Tereza Capelos (University of Southampton), Mikko Salmela (UH), Karen Celis (VuB), Thomas Legein (VuB), Domenico Di Siena (DemSoc), Zsolt Nagy (DemSoc)
8.0	08.01.2025	Reviewed and given comments	Alina Mozolevska (PMBSNU), Mikko Salmela (UH) and Emilia Palonen (UH)
8.0	10.01.2025	Revised and Finalised after the review and feedback	Gulnaz Sharafutdinova (KCL), Ayhan Kaya (Bilgi)

Table of contents

- Executive Summary 4
- 1. Introduction 5
 - 1.1. About PLEDGE 5
 - 1.2. Objectives of D1.1 5
 - 1.3. Targets of D1.1 5
 - 1.4. Methodology 5
- 2. Emotions and Grievance Politics: State of the Art 6
 - 2.1. Introduction 6
 - 2.2. Analytical Frames, Theories and Concepts 7
 - 2.2.1 Populism, Far-Right Radicalization, Affective Polarization: Demand and Supply Side Drivers 6
 - 2.2.2 Emotions, Emotional Dynamics and Emotional Mechanisms 11
 - 2.2.3 Cognitive Approaches 13
 - 2.3 Methodological Challenges 14
 - 2.4 Future Research Agenda 16
 - 2.5 Policy Implications from Recent Scholarship 19
- 3. Conclusions 22
 - 3.1 Summary of the Key Findings and results of the deliverable 22
 - 3.2 Limitations of the Deliverable 22
 - 3.3 Recommendations for Future Actions 23
- 4. Bibliography 24

Executive Summary

The 'First Needs Analysis Report' provides an overview of the recent scholarship on the issues of grievance-driven, emotional politics. In recent years, this sphere of research has been developing with increasing intensity and conceptual, analytical, and methodological innovation. The report identifies central scholarly trends and findings, and emerging methodological and empirical challenges.

The analytical frames, theories and concepts employed by the scholarship on emotional and grievance politics often focus on demand and supply side drivers and would benefit from an additional engagement with interactive effects, feedback loops and concepts that allow for recognizing and engaging with a richer understanding of emotions, emotional clusters, and emotional mechanisms.

Methodological challenges faced by the scholarship on grievance politics arise from its association with various methods, disciplines, and the complexity (as well as diversity) of concept operationalization. The ongoing evolution of the forms taken by resentment and emotional politics leads to a constant rethink of the conceptual frameworks and operationalization processes. By identifying these methodological and conceptual challenges, this report suggests developing an integrated analytical and conceptual framework that could enable cross-country research and be flexible for employment in the context of qualitative and quantitative methods. This new framework will allow PLEDGE to analyse the value of emotionality in the policy processes, recognize in grievance politics the strongly felt emotional needs and demands of citizens and groups, and identify mechanisms of emotional signals to facilitate the integration of emotional politics into policymaking processes.

Future policy implications in emotional and grievance politics relate to the challenges of developing effective communication strategies with the voters. These strategies will provide opportunities to reinforce representative relationships through the reliance on democratic design and allow policymakers to strengthen their communication by moving away from negative associations of emotional politics and harnessing their potential for political mobilization in the pursuit of pro-social and pro-democratic objectives and future.

1. Introduction

1.1. About PLEDGE

PLEDGE is a Horizon Europe-funded project focusing on the emotional dynamics of political grievances and their implications for democratic politics. The PLEDGE project engages researchers, policymakers, and citizens in a collective effort to better understand citizens' emotions and develop practices and tools that promote emotionally responsive democratic governance and political communication, and foster pro-democratic forms of civic engagement.

1.2. Objectives of D1.1

This deliverable was developed in the context of WP1.1, which has the key objectives of

- providing a systematic review of the extant knowledge on grievance politics, emotions, and policy-making,
- developing a map of related previous and ongoing EU-funded projects,
- producing a meta-analysis of the data in the Consortium Databank.

This First Needs Analysis Report will include stakeholder input (through WP6 and WP7).

1.3. Targets of D1.1

This deliverable is addressed mainly to the members of the PLEDGE consortium to provide a shared vision of the existing knowledge, challenges and needs of the project.

1.4. Methodology

To develop this report, first, with input from all members of the PLEDGE consortium, we collected a database of recent

publications on grievance politics, emotions and radicalization. We then summarized each publication noting the main research questions, conceptual apparatus, methodology, findings and agenda for future research. Additionally, we collected similar information about all EU-funded projects that have dealt with the various aspects of grievance politics including issues of affective polarization, populism, emotions, and radicalization. The report was written based on these two sources of information.

2. Emotions and Grievance Politics: State of the Art

2.1. Introduction

The role of emotions in politics is not a new subject of inquiry. The heightened scholarly attention to this subject over the past decade and a half is associated with the global rise of populist and radicalized (most often far-right) politics and an increasing use of emotions as a mechanism for political mobilization. Given its political significance, scholars have approached this subject from various disciplinary perspectives including political science, political and social psychology, economics, sociology, political communication, and anthropology; as well as different methodological orientations encompassing various qualitative and quantitative methods. In this document, we systematically review the existing literature focusing on the main analytical, conceptual and methodological approaches that have guided contemporary scholars. We highlight ongoing innovation in scholarly approaches and point out the emerging challenges and potential solutions.

Emotions are ‘the residue of lived experiences,’ and the current politics of grievances are also intrinsically associated with real-life crises, events, and processes (Petersen 2017). Specifically, the key events that shaped contemporary politics in the European Union include the 2008 global financial crisis, the 2015 refugee crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, the Russo-Ukrainian war that started in full in 2022, the climate crisis and the energy transition-related crisis. These various crises and lived experiences create the demand for the ideas and politics that are responded to by political entrepreneurs who harness the emotional energy associated with individual responses to these crises. Most often, these are populist politicians associated with the far-right political parties who instrumentalize and foster anger, frustration, and insecurity, who propagate distrust in democracy, capitalize on the narratives of victimhood and resentment and cause affective polarization in their society. Both the demand and supply side of grievance-fueled politics are important and, if anything, scholarly attention needs to be given to their interactive effects, which makes such politics intoxicating and to creative solutions that can offer a pathway out of the vicious cycle triggered by such interactions.

This report begins with a focus on analytical frames and concepts that scholars developed and relied on to explore these socio-political developments. It then touches on methodological challenges and solutions, future research agenda and the central policy implications from the most recent scholarship on grievance-fueled politics.

2.2. Analytical Frames, Theories and Concepts

2.2.1 Populism, Far-Right Radicalization, and Affective Polarization: Demand and Supply Side Drivers

The study of the role of emotions and grievances in global politics has been closely associated with the scholarship on populism and far-right politics which transcended disciplinary boundaries. In the US political context, in particular, this subject is often approached through *affective polarization* which was introduced to capture the increasing and impassioned animosity between the two main political parties and their followers in the US (Iyengar et al., 2019). In and out of the European Union, the focus is more on *far-right politics* and *political radicalization* responding to an increasing electoral success of far-right parties in Europe (Golder 2016). Polarization in Europe was also studied, for example, in the context of the EU-funded H2020 project “Building Resilience Against Violent Extremism and Polarisation” (or BRaVE). Scholars have generally split into studying the demand side factors that can explain the proliferation of grievances, their associated emotions, and their political implications and the supply side of support for such politics and political actors that focus on political style, leadership, and discourses.

Demand Side Drivers

Demand side approaches cover various themes from strictly materialist perspectives to post-materialist, cultural, and symbolic as well as psychological:

- a. Urban-rural divide approaches are more materialist in the sense that they highlight the unequal distribution of resources and opportunities as causes of resentment and frustration among rural populations (Goodwin and Heath 2016; Guilluy 2018; Cramer 2016).
- b. Cultural backlash theory focuses on younger generations' postmaterialist and progressive values and their tension with older conservatives (Inglehart & Norris 2019).
- c. Socio-economic factors such as economic hardship, unemployment and income inequality (Arzheimer 2009; Vlandas and Halikiopoulou 2019; Pontusson and Weisstanner 2018; Jesuit et al. 2009), local marginalization (Bock 2016; Rydgren and Ruth 2013) and demographic changes related to immigration (Arzheimer 2009; Rydgren and Ruth 2013; Stockemer et al. 2018), also predict support for radical right-wing parties. Erdogan and Uyan-Semerci (2020) have explored the rise of xenophobia and exclusion in Adana (Turkey) and argued that anti-immigrant attitudes were a response to the influx of Syrians to Turkey following the Syrian civil war and the way perceived economic problems and specifically unemployment were linked to these immigrants.
- d. Psychological and emotional factors highlight the role of personality, conspiracy mentality, threat sensitivity, and anxiety as well as nostalgic deprivation (Bakker et al. 2016; Erisen et al.

2021; Gest et al. 2018). Nostalgic deprivation has been defined as “the discrepancy between individuals’ understandings of their current status and their perceptions about their past” (Gest et al. 2018). As such this concept is linked to social identity-focused approaches emphasizing insecure identity, recognition, and the dynamics of othering (Hirvonen and Pennanen 2019; Honneth 1996). Other recent studies have explored the ideational underpinning of fear among the supporters of far-right and found that in Germany, for example, fear reflects Islamophobia and perceptions of cultural threat to the collective ‘we’ associated with religious cleavages (Diefenbach and von Scheve 2023). Some studies focus on deep emotional needs expressed through emotionally evocative narratives shared by individuals and groups (onsite and online) (Capelos et al. 2018).

Studies on the demand side that point to psychological factors do at times run into the problem of potential endogeneity and cannot account for the role of media in the proliferation of specific views and predispositions.

- e. Huntingtonian civilisational paradigm: Since the dissolution of the Socialist block and the war in the former Yugoslavia, a culturalist discourse has been revitalised in a way that fuelled the debates around the decline of multiculturalism and the rise of the clash of civilisations narrative (Huntington 1996). Accordingly, civilisations, particularly Christianity and Islam, are believed to be incompatible and unable to coexist (Huntington 1996). Huntington’s attempt to reduce civilisation to religion and culture, departing from earlier sociological and philosophical trends that considered industrialisation, capitalism, colonialism, and urbanisation as defining factors (Elias 1998), found a receptive audience globally, including within the European Union. Huntingtonian civilisational paradigm has also brought about the “co-radicalisation” of young people with native and migrant backgrounds essentialising the boundaries between these groups and fostering ideological extremism (Pyszczynski et al. 2008; Kaya 2021).
- f. Spatial factors: Scientific research has already provided evidence that native youths often labelled as “far-right extremists” come from backgrounds of independent farmers and small shopkeepers, primarily residing in politically and geographically remote areas (Rodrigues-Pose 2018). These youths, influenced by global political and economic forces that have promoted hegemonic masculinities, respond to the erosion of public and domestic patriarchy by asserting their entitlement to restore patriarchy in both spheres. They believe that the liberal and Europeanised political elite, along with the newly “empowered minorities” women, immigrants, and refugees, have taken away their ancient patriarchal power, thereby becoming more active in contemporary international economic and political life. The rural and lower-middle-class youth, experiencing downward mobility, find themselves caught between the forces of global capitalism and an indifferent or even complicit political elite that exacerbates their predicament. These “losers of globalization” harbour resentment towards global capitalism, Europeanisation, diversity, labour mobility, cosmopolitanism, and international migration (Rodrigues-Pose 2018; Horner et al. 2018; Kaya 2019). They capitalise on notions of masculinity, imagined patriarchy, heritage, national past, nationalism, nativism, and nostalgic backward-looking perspectives, longing for a time when they felt entitled to their perceived positions in society. Populist political figures exploit such tenets as cultural capital to counter the adverse effects of

globalisation through mediated actions (Kimmel 2003; Köttig et al. 2017; Kaya and Kayaoglu 2017).

- g. Political factors: Others have argued that Western democratic systems of political representation indeed have various representation gaps (e.g., in terms of education, income, ethnic background, etc.) and that there has been a substantial increase in the role and power of non-majoritarian institutions (e.g., EMF, Worldbank, etc.). This tends to promote political views and policy positions that facilitate, for example, rather liberal and cosmopolitan attitudes and leads to anger and frustration on the side of those holding different views and policy preferences (e.g., Zürn 2022; Landwehr 2022).

Supply Side Drivers

Studies of the supply side of populist and far-right politics have brought attention to political entrepreneurs themselves and their role in instigating threat perceptions and stimulating anxieties in relation to a variety of issues such as immigration and refugee crisis, corrupt elites and public institutions that cannot be trusted (Huber et al. 2021; Calvillo et al. 2020; Esses et al. 2017). This scholarship has focused specifically on the authoritarian populist *political style*, the *discursive content* and emotional (affective) *strategies* used by populist leaders seeking to build a popular following.

Moffitt and Thorney (2014) defined political style as “the repertoires of performance that are used to create political relations.” Populists commonly appeal to ‘the people’ and make references to crises, breakdowns, and various types of threats. These could include threats associated with immigration or social changes, economic degradation, or emergency of terrorism. They also advocate for quick, simple and radical solutions, and they do it in a more colorful, direct form, often using slang language and juxtaposing their style to the more serious, formal, rational and arguments-driven mainstream political style. The political style-focused argument was advanced as an alternative to two other supply-style arguments. One is focused on the discursive specificity of populist politics that develops an anti-status quo discourse and simplifies politics into the opposition between ‘the people’ and ‘the other’ (Laclau and Mouffe 2014; Stavrakakis 2017). The other one views populism as “a political strategy through which a personalistic leader seeks or exercises government power based on direct, unmediated, noninstitutionalized support from large numbers of mostly unorganized followers” (Weyland 2001; Roberts 2006).

The issue of leadership, generally, is an important topic for the supply-side-leaning scholars of emotional politics. Leaders can provide ontological security to insecure people, argues Kinnvall (2019) based on her analysis of the leadership of India’s president. Modi has re-invented ‘nationhood’, ‘religion’ and ‘Hindu masculinity’ along gendered lines and thereby created a foundation for governing practices aimed at ‘healing’ ontological insecurities manifested in Indian society. Kösen and Erdoğan (2023) show how Azerbaijan’s President Aliyev prepared, mobilized and motivated society during the Nagorno-Karabakh War in 2020 through multiple speeches that aimed to evoke specific emotions such as shame, pride, and humiliation. Similarly, Szabó and Szabo (2022) studied Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán’s delegitimation discourse on the European Union in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. Other scholars have studied the political communication practices and strategies by political actors, policymakers, and

opinion leaders in other country contexts to address as well as construct and amplify grievances (onsite and online) (Capelos et al. 2018; Kazlauskaite and Salmela 2022; Kinnvall and Svensson 2023; Sharafutdinova 2020).

The EU-funded H2020 project “Populism And Civic Engagement” (PaCE) has also underlined the importance of political leadership for countering populist politics and suggested it to be crucial that liberal-democratic parties and leaders develop positive narratives that include a vision of the future and suggest mechanisms of empowerment to individuals and communities.

Interactive Dynamics and Effects

The more recent explorations highlight the interaction between supply and demand factors noting important linkages between the appeals the far-right parties make and the expressed ideas and concerns of their followers. Kaya (2019), for example, explores the phenomenon of heritage populism in Germany, where the AfD leverages historical narratives and cultural heritage to mobilize support, emphasizing local identity, anti-Muslim racism, and opposition to multiculturalism. Based on interviews with young AfD supporters, Kaya illustrates how these individuals express socio-economic, spatial, and nostalgic deprivation, finding solace in the party’s nativist and populist radicalism. Kaya argues that the rise of right-wing populism is driven by the exploitation of Islamophobic and xenophobic sentiments, and the strategic use of cultural heritage to craft a compelling narrative of identity and belonging; he emphasizes it is necessary to understand the context of broader socio-economic and political frustrations and address the root causes of disenchantment to counter the appeal of right-wing populism.

Nguyen et al. (2021) develop an analytical framework distinguishing between the ‘demand side’ of emotions, which refers to the electorate’s pre-existing emotional states and their influence on political support, and the ‘supply side’, which involves the strategic elicitation of emotions by RRP parties through their discourse and political style. This dual perspective allows for a comprehensive analysis of how emotions are both a cause and effect of political mobilization and support.

Going beyond the top-down approach to the instrumentalization of the past by populist leaders, Bilewicz and Liu (2020) and; Bilewicz (2022) also emphasize the interactive dynamics between collective victimhood and adaptation to historical trauma and conspiracy theories. This sense of victimhood resulting from a social adaptation to historical conflicts resonates with populist narratives and is related to the rise of right-wing populism (Capelos, Nield and Salmela 2023).

2.2.2 Emotions, Emotional Dynamics and Emotional Mechanisms

Political psychology studies that focus on emotionality as a determinant of political preferences have, in the past, been limited to the study of anger and fear (Brader 2006; Albertson and Gadarian 2012; Huddy et al. 2008; Jost et al. 2017; Mayer and Nguyen 2021). Recent research on populism and emotional politics has revealed that anger and anxiety normally conceal other emotions and feelings of insecurity, uncertainty, humiliation, envy, shame, and resentment (Salmela and von Scheve 2017, 2018; Salmela and Capelos 2021; Capelos et al. 2022; Sullivan 2021; Kaya 2019, 2021; Kaya et al.

2021). Therefore, studying the emotional economy of grievance politics requires more focus on these underlying emotions and emotional dynamics that reflect frustration and disillusionment in response to a sense of injustice and marginalization. Over the past years, there has been a significant advancement in the understanding of the emotional underpinnings of populist politics including the emotional needs of individuals and groups who actively engage in demonstrations, protests, and activism (on-site and/or online) and those who are silent and passive (Capelos et al. 2022; Capelos and Demertzis 2022; Salmela and Capelos 2021; Sullivan 2021; Kinnvall and Singh 2022; Knops 2023; Celis et al. 2021).

Salmela and von Scheve (2018) found partially dissimilar emotional processes driving right- and left-wing populism and, specifically, in the targets of right- and left-wing resentment. While fear and insecurities experienced in contemporary societies, and associated with them anger, resentment, and hatred, may be shared, those responsible for the outcomes differ across political lines. The left blames a political and economic establishment responsible for austerity politics, while the right blames political and cultural elites accused of favoring ethnic, religious, and sexual out-groups at the expense of the neglected in-group. Referring to partially different emotional opportunity structures and distinct political strategies for exploiting these structures, the authors suggested that right-wing populism is characterized by repressed shame that transforms fear and insecurity into anger, resentment, and hatred against perceived “enemies” of the precarious self. Left-wing populism, in turn, associates more with acknowledged shame that allows individuals to self-identify as aggrieved and humiliated by neoliberal policies and their advocates. The latter type of shame holds emancipatory potential as it allows individuals to establish bonds with others who feel the same, whereas repressors remain in their shame or seek bonds from repression-mediated defensive anger and hatred. Earlier, Salmela and von Scheve (2017) suggested that emotional processes that affect people’s identities are responsible for the current popularity of the new radical right, not only among low- and medium-skilled workers, but also among the middle classes whose insecurities manifest as fears of not being able to live up to salient social identities and their constitutive values, and as shame about this actual or anticipated inability. Focusing on the link between fear and shame they argued that this is particularly salient in contemporary capitalist societies where responsibility for success and failure is increasingly individualized, and failure is stigmatized through unemployment, receiving welfare benefits, or labor migration.

Additionally, some recent studies in the sphere of emotionality have tried to move away from a more discrete approach to emotions (studying specific emotions such as anger, fear, or pride) and towards developing methods to study affect and emotions as more complex systems that involve affect clusters and recognize that citizens express their emotionality in rich terms. These clusters are linked to appraisals of multiple political objects and reflect aversive, anxious, loss and gain-oriented emotional responses (Capelos and Chrona 2018). Capelos et al. (2024) undertook a comprehensive examination of reactionism, resentment, and collective narcissism, collectively termed the “anti-social triad of grievance politics.” Although these constructs are conceptually distinct, they are psychologically intricately linked and constitute a potent blend of anti-social sentiments within grievance politics. This study pioneered in establishing original connections between these interlinked phenomena providing empirical evidence of their coexistence and interactions. They have introduced a novel scale to measure reactionism and explore its associations with existing measures of *resentment* and collective narcissism, as well as their associations with values, authoritarianism, and populism.

discrete approach to emotions is theorizing on *emotional mechanisms* with a specific focus on the emotional mechanism of resentment. Resentment is central to understanding the psychological foundations of reactionary politics, right-wing populism, Islamic fundamentalism, and radicalism. Salice and Salmela (2022) advanced an account of emotional mechanisms (EMs) as personal, often unconscious, distinctively patterned, mental processes whereby an emotion of a given kind is transmuted into an emotion of a different kind. Then, Salmela and Capelos (2021) approached *resentment* as an emotional mechanism that worked to reinforce a morally superior sense of victimhood through a process of transvaluation: what was once desired or valued, yet unattainable, was reassessed as something undesirable, and one's own self from being inferior, a loser, is reassessed as being noble and superior. The negative emotions of envy, shame, and inefficacious anger are the main triggers of resentment, with their associated feelings of inferiority and impotence, which target the vulnerable self. The outcomes of resentment are other-directed negative emotions of resentment, indignation, and hatred, reinforced and validated by social sharing. Salmela et al. (2024) then drew on contemporary studies that center on collective resentment in political contexts (Sharafutdinova 2020; Medvedev 2023; Illouz 2023) to determine under which conditions and which elements of this emotional mechanism shift from the individual to the collective level or emerge at the collective level from the outset.

Capelos et al. (2023) relied on the analytical framework of resentment to examine toxic masculinity, anti-feminist, anti-globalisation, and anti-military conscription positions in the narratives of what constitutes success and failure among young South Korean men during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study demonstrated that the content of these narratives of success and failure in resentment related to the electoral win of the right-wing People Power party in March 2022 which capitalised on anti-feminist grievances.

Finally, another promising new framework (Sullivan 2021) focused on *affective practices* to show how resentful affects are created, facilitated, and transformed into sharing or suppressing populist political views and practices. This framework moved scholarship beyond a focus on illiberal and anti-elite discourses to explore populism as a practice that is embodied and enacted in “past-focused” and “change-resistant” everyday actions and in relation to opportunities that “sediment” affect-laden political positions and identities.

Collective and Group-based Emotions

The research on emotions in politics progressed in both directions: understanding individual-level emotions and emotional mechanisms and collective-level emotions and their dynamics. Sullivan and Day (2019) explored the interrelationship between pride and shame in group-based and collective forms. Building upon seminal work by Cooley (1902) and Scheff (2013) they highlighted patterns of complex, dynamic relations between occurrences of group-based pride, group-based shame, collective pride and collective shame in prototypical group contexts of celebration, competition and conflict. This novel analysis found that mixtures of negative group pride and anger evident in collective hubris or contempt and some forms of aggression directed towards other groups are not necessarily produced by repression of collective shame.

Salmela and Sullivan (2022) have explored in more depth group-based pride, distinguishing between the shape and size of this emotion and looking at the conditions in which group-based pride was rationally appropriate. The research on collective emotions was greatly boosted through studies of collective

victimhood, particularly in Eastern European countries. Bilewicz and Liu (2020) explore the concept of collective victimhood as an adaptive mechanism in societies experiencing adverse conditions such as wars, conflicts, occupations, and crises.

Lipinski and Szabo (2023) bring together collective memory scholarship and populism to analyse the commemorative narratives of the competing populist right-wing political parties in Hungary and Poland promoted during national celebrations. Their findings reveal that victimisation and heroisation are constant and stable components of both countries' political narratives. Moreover, the elements of populist communication are articulated alongside nationalist themes emphasizing the greatness of the nation, historical revisionism or national Catholicism. The references to the people using ethno-cultural and exclusionary terms are of particular significance. Although praised and credited with positive qualities, the Polish and Hungarian peoples are more frequently presented as victims of international enemies, European elites or internal, cultural and political elites. This victimhood status allows political actors to both represent themselves as advocates of the people and legitimise their claims.

2.2.3 Cognitive Approaches

Psychological research on radicalization and populism brings into light the significant role of conspiracy theories and beliefs among populist, far-right and far-left voters (Bilewicz and Liu 2020; Bilewicz 2022; Bilewicz and Imhoff 2022). Historical perspectives help to uncover the historical antecedents of conspiracy theories: they are often associated with historical traumas, a sense of victimhood, powerlessness, and status devaluation that accompany historical trauma (Bilewicz 2022). Conspiracy theories could even be used as a measurement of collective victimhood and its global differences in coping mechanisms between the centre and peripheries (Bilewicz and Liu 2020). As such, these cognitively oriented studies that focus on ideas and beliefs suggest the centrality of emotional underpinnings of these beliefs and call for integrating cognitive and emotions-focused approaches to recognize the overlaps and interactions in these two spheres.

The ongoing EU-funded research project “Populism and Conspiracy Theories” (PaCT) has found that, while conspiracy theories are popular both among left- and right-wing populist movements, they are more important for right-wing parties and organizations. Another EU-funded project “Partnership against violent radicalization in the cities” (PRACTICIES) suggested that conspiratorial thinking needs to be countered through education and critical thinking development.

Cognitive approaches that focus on ideological convictions have inquired into issues of vaccine hesitancy. A study by Bilewicz and Soral (2022) found that the relationship between Right-wing authoritarianism (RWA) and attitudes toward vaccination may be different in countries where leaders voiced anti-vaccination views and suggested the need for further large-scale cross-cultural studies. Further studies should investigate how to utilize knowledge about the ideological basis of vaccine hesitancy, and what arguments should be high to persuade individuals with high and low RWA and SDO (social dominance orientation).

2.3 Methodological Challenges

Conceptual pluralism

The scholarship on grievance politics has traditionally drawn on a variety of methods from different disciplines and productively combined rigorous quantitative analysis with in-depth historical and interpretative qualitative studies. The ongoing conceptual and analytical innovation also created a demand for creating new instruments for operationalizing and measuring new concepts. Methodological challenges related to the complexity of *conceptualizing* such a complex and multi-layered emotion as resentment, for example, produced different scholarly frameworks illustrating the absence of consensus about the conceptual framework. First, resentment, as an emotional mechanism and long-term affective attitude, is differentiated from the broader affective category of resentment (Salmela and von Scheve 2018; Salmela and Szanto 2024). Knops et al. (2023) examine resentment rather than resentment from three-dimensional conceptual framework: morality, complexity and temporality, whereas Demertzis (2006) differentiates the Nietzschean and non-Nietzschean approaches to resentment. Finally, Salmela and Capelos (2021) theorize four stages of resentment: the ‘triggering stage’, the ‘initiating stage’, the ‘advancing stage’ and the ‘consolidating stage’. This model aims to explain the development of the affective drivers of resentment and their strengthening in the political sphere. Although these perspectives are not incompatible, their multiplicity creates a lack of clarity in the conceptual framework of resentment. To answer these challenges, Capelos and Demertzis (2022) reviewed and updated the 6-item scale of resentment to apply it to a populist European context.

However, there are also others such as Salmela and Szanto (2024) argue that there is already a consensus emerging about the understanding of resentment rather than a lack of clarity which may have been there in the past. Salmela and Szanto (2024: 5) state that resentment serves to cope with frustration and perceived threats to self-esteem and social validation through two concurrent processes of value transformation. Initially, previously desired but unattainable goals are reinterpreted as undesirable or insignificant, leading to the adoption of alternative values. Simultaneously, the individual's self-perception shifts from viewing themselves as a failure or inferior to embracing an identity characterized by nobility and superiority.

The difficulty of conceptualizing emotions and grievance politics is related to the interdisciplinary of these concepts. Analyzing these concepts also means that they are impacted by the neuroanatomic and neurobiological functioning of social feelings (Eslinger et al. 2021). For example, approaching anger as a social feeling allows its consideration from a neuroscience perspective (Eslinger et al. 2021). It therefore raises more questions about how social feelings as results of interactive social behaviors can fuel resentment.

Similar to the conceptual framework of resentment, approaches to populism have often been contested. Recent studies have focused on the combination of ideational and discursive approaches to populism studies (Lipinski and Szabo 2023). However, Kinnvall and Svensson (2019; 2022) denounce the binarity of these earlier approaches to populism as either an ideology or a style of politics. Contrary to that, they explore populism from the perspective of research on ontological insecurity which combines the psychological and structural aspects of populist politics. This framework enables the authors to discuss both ‘everyday’ far-right populism and the role of national leadership (in

their case Indian) as an ontological security provider through foreign policy discourse. In both contexts, the ontological insecurity approach to populism reveals the racial and gendered dynamics at play. Other recent approaches focus on the anthropological and spatial definition of populism as ‘a discourse of disempowered individuals living in remote places to curb their political, social, economic, spatial and nostalgic deprivation’ (Kaya 2023).

However, the analysis of emotions in politics is not limited to populism and resentment. Scholars have emphasized other concepts using, for example, a feminist approach (Celis and Childs 2020; Celis and Childs 2023), the place of emotions in IR (Kosen and Erdogan 2023), and the mechanism of emotional distancing that is a part of resentment (Salmela and von Scheve 2017). These pluralities of analytical frameworks demonstrate that emotions and grievances-driven politics are approached using different terms and concepts (resentimentful politics, polarized politics, populism, etc.). These theories and concepts are developed and used in different disciplines including political psychology, neuroscience, IR, phenomenology and macro-historical sociology.

Data Collection: balancing the variety of sources and accessing marginalized groups

Scholars of emotions and grievance politics have relied on various types of data. Most empirical research utilized qualitative data including speeches (Erçetin and Erdogan 2018; Palau-Sampio and Carratalá 2022; Kaya 2023a; Kosen and Erdogan 2023; Lipinski and Szabo 2023), newspaper articles (Erçetin and Erdogan 2021; Kiss 2021; Kazlauskaite and Salmela 2022), interviews (Capelos and Chrona 2018; Capelos, Salmela and Krisciunaite 2022; Diefenbach and von Scheve 2023; Kaya 2023a; 2023b; Robert and Kaya 2023; Ingelgom, Amara-Hammou and Celis forthcoming), focus groups (Erdogan and Semerci 2020; Celis et al. 2021; Ingelgom, Amara-Hammou and Celis forthcoming; Knops et al. forthcoming) or data collected through surveys (Capelos, Nield and Salmela 2023; Nguyen, Salmela and von Scheve 2021; Knops et al. forthcoming). Many of these studies combine more than one approach, resulting from the complexity of conceptualizing emotions and grievance politics. However, the spectrum of tools propagating emotions and ideas rapidly evolved with new technologies. Kazlauskaite (2022; 2023) examined how the immersive Virtual Experience (VR) ‘A Postcard from the Uprising’ at the Museum of the Second World War in Gdansk, Poland creates a resentimentful emotional regime. This study noted the role of VR in transmitting resentment through re-experiencing perceived injustice and victimhood, helping PiS to harness these feelings among museum visitors.

Accessing data represents a significant challenge in the study of emotions and grievances in politics. Populations that feel the most resentful are often marginalized and exposed to epistemic injustice as they were clustered in distinct categories by previous research (Kaya and Benevento 2022). However, scholars have highlighted the significance of in-depth interviews to reveal the emotional experiences associated with the support for right-wing populist parties (Salmela and von Scheve 2017; 2018). Kaya and Benevento’s (2022) method of cooperation between senior and novice researchers enables scholars to access groups that are labelled as far-right in Europe and to develop more authentic research with self-identified Muslim youth. The significant variety of data can be both an advantage and a challenge for researchers who might need to adapt new methods of analysis.

textual data in social science

The importance of language and the instrumentalization of emotions in media are a significant dimension of modern political communication (Mandenaki and Mourlas 2018; Kazlauskaitė and Salmela 2022; Palau-Sampio and Carratalá 2022). To account for this key constitutive dimension, Mandenaki and Mourlas (2018) adapted the discursive approach to populism by using automatic textual data analysis. Contrary to manual content analysis, automatic textual data analysis enables researchers to detect populism and frame its evolution in a vast amount of digital text (Mandenaki and Mourlas 2018). As populist discourse is massively spread through online media outlets and social media, this method provides solutions to the challenges faced by large digital text collections. For example, artificial intelligence facilitates lexicometric analysis (Mandenaki and Mourlas 2018). The authors highlight how this quantitative approach might sharpen the qualitative ones already used in research on populism (Mandenaki and Mourlas 2018).

Furthermore, quantitative analysis has been used with qualitative analysis, particularly for the analysis of populist discourse in media (Palau-Sampio and Carratalá 2022; Palau-Sampio 2023). Palau-Sampio and Carratalá (2022; 2023) analyse comparatively the content in pseudo-media and how the polarization of clickbait techniques is used in the discourse of the far-right wing in Spain. Although the authors prioritize a qualitative method, they also emphasize that a quantitative approach would allow them to further delve into the expressive patterns used in pseudo-media. From a comparative perspective, Herkman and Palonen (2024) have been studying political communication in social media in election campaigning for the European Parliament. This offers an excellent basis for exploring affective communication. While Twitter is not available for 2024 research, audiovisual social media has possibilities for further analysis (Szebeni and Salojärvi 2022; Salojärvi et al. 2023).

Illustrating the need for new methods of data analysis, Capelos and Chrona (2018) created a new mapping methodology to analyse affect clusters and systems. The authors introduce mapping methodology as a rigorous way of capturing the complexity of affect clusters and systems. In their work, Capelos and Chrona (2018) argue that moving beyond a handful of discrete emotions toward a careful examination of the cognitive representations of specific affect clusters and systems can make it possible for the researcher to engage seriously with the content of the expression of anger, hope, pride, joy, irritation, fear, worry, concern, disappointment, and loss in various contexts. They use a variant of Cognitive Affective Naps to reveal the depth and richness of emotions in the context of political orientations in Turkey (Capelos and Chrona 2018).

As previous research on political emotions and grievances, PLEDGE will face various methodological challenges. The first one would be to develop a conceptual framework accounting for the interdisciplinarity and the complexity of resentment and populism. As a transnational project, PLEDGE will have to adapt concepts and theories often used in one (European) country case study to other country contexts. These challenges will be amplified by the variety of data analysis methods available and the necessity to combine and adapt them to rapidly evolving data.

2.4 Future Research Agenda

Funded by
the European Union

While some emotions have received greater scholarly attention,

others, such as disappointment, envy, guilt, and resentment, as well as joy, empathy, and gratitude are less studied. Second, since individual emotional experiences are ever-changing and are in constant interaction with values, identities, and political orientations, there is a need to explore such interactive dynamics, loops and interconnections. Extant approaches offer a fragmented, often one-sided account of the emotional economy of grievance politics. What we need is an integrated approach that synthesizes these theories under one analytical framework, that captures how emotions inter-relate, how they change and how they interact with identities and values. This conceptual lacuna is broadened further by the lack of empirical measures (Capelos and Demertzis 2018). The conceptual and empirical complexity of the emotionality of grievances explains but does not excuse the scarcity of a parsimonious explanatory framework.

A similar challenge is evident in policy analysis. Extant studies document the importance of emotions in governmental policy-making (Boon et al. 2021), foreign policy (Hutchison and Bleiker 2014), and the reputations of non-governmental actors. While some studies recognize that citizens, politicians, and administrators are emotional actors engaging in emotional deliberative processes and their emotions need to be studied (Fischer 2010), the majority contrasts rationality to emotionality, often giving preference to rational processes and outcomes. What is missing is knowledge on how to harness the value of emotionality in the policy process, particularly when delivered through grievances, and design meaningful opportunities for taking part in policymaking and policies responsive to the emotional needs of citizens (Maor and Capelos 2020; Manners 2014). PLEDGE recognizes this value and will develop practical knowledge to be used in the policy process. Such innovation can be found in studies of participatory and deliberative democracy techniques within and outside the institutions of representative democracy (Scharfbillig et al. 2021). The emergence of enthusiasm, happiness, anger, disappointment, and frustration is engendered by particular design features of deliberative practices (Johnson et al. 2019; Morrell et al. 2022; Morrell 2013, 2018). While individual and shared emotions partially bridge different values and identities in deliberative practices (Celis and Childs 2020, 2023), insight is embryonic into how and through which democratic innovations and interventions can the desirable emotional outcomes be implemented. These studies stress the need for theoretical and empirical projects that design emotionally sensitive governance practices and processes.

Advancing the state of the art will take place through recognizing in grievance politics the strongly felt emotional needs and demands of citizens and groups. These emotional signals of disaffection, frustration and insecurities exist in dynamic interactions with individual and group identities, values, beliefs, and political practices. PLEDGE will have to develop a framework that identifies the mechanisms producing these signals and empirically decodes them into operationalizable measures and indicators across countries and contexts. This framework will be innovative in its practice of science, by being developed through co-creation with stakeholders designed as a Democratic Innovation project, driven by democratic sensibility (following design science practices, Schuler and Namioka 1993; Sanders and Stappers 2008). This project will aim to produce knowledge, tools, and practices, and facilitate the integration of the emotional dimension of politics into policymaking processes in ways that promote pro-democratic forms of expressing grievances and break the cycle of negative, toxic, victimhood-driven anti-social political processes.

campaigns. They have identified the patterns of political nostalgia in Facebook communications in Hungary in the run-up to the 2019 European parliamentary election. More comparative studies would help (see e.g. Herkman and Palonen 2024; Salojärvi et al. 2023). A common call for future research is the necessity for a global, gender-focused and feminist approach in the scholarship on emotions and grievances. Although the feminist approach has been used by some scholars, it is still an emerging topic in recent literature and an imperative for future research (Mandenaki and Mourlas 2018).

Authors have highlighted that conspiracy theories research (Bilewicz 2022) and studies on resentment focused on Western democracies (Capelos, Salmela & Krisciunaite 2022), and far Eastern democracies (Capelos, Nield and Salmela 2023). This overlooks the global differences and the distinct dynamics in core and peripheral countries (Bilewicz and Liu 2020). This issue is also relevant to the conceptual framework of resentment as the 6-item scale of Capelos and Demertzis (2022) has only been applied to a European populist context.

Future research also needs to consider the evolving methodological challenges of research on emotions and grievance politics. Vast textual data is at the core of these studies. Populist discourses and narratives are rapidly evolving and spreading in new forms of media outlets. Methods of quantitative analysis such as the one developed by Mandenaki and Mourlas (2018) could be complementary to already used qualitative methods. Their combination would allow a rapid adaptation to the increasing amount of data by improving Emotional Lexicon accuracy and Part of Speech tagging. This method would also enable the collection and analysis of larger data, a limitation emphasized in current scholarship (Capelos and Chorna 2018; Palau-Sampio and Carratalá 2022; Capelos, Nield and Salmela 2023). The empirical research on emotional politics also needs to pay greater attention to visual data. Mozolevska (2024) has explored the important role of visual narratives in Russian and Ukrainian digital participatory cultures, revealing their role in trauma coping and identity construction processes in the time of war (particularly for Ukraine). Furthermore, given the rapid technological transformation, it is important to explore the role of new technologies in propagating certain emotions and ideas with specific political implications. The VR experience in Gdansk is one example of the role of these new technological tools in the formation of affective communities and regimes (Kazlauskaite 2022). Adapting methodology to the new hybrid media system will be essential for researchers to understand how discourses based on emotions and resentment adapt to this evolving context and generate new (dis)information tools (Palau-Sampio 2023). The platforms operationalised for political communication change, from the election time Twitter (Herkman and Palonen 2024) to new forms of audiovisual communication. Therefore, the multiplicity and multifaceted nature of emotions and politics calls for the development of a scholarship based on interdisciplinary and mixed-method research designs.

Building on the emerging scholarships on political emotions as drivers of left-wing populism (Salmela and von Scheve 2018; Bilewicz and Imhoff 2022; Salmela and Szanto 2024), research should include the analysis of populist discourse in far-left-wing pseudo-media (Palau-Sampio and Carratalá 2022; Palau-Sampio 2023). Kiss (2021) demonstrated that in Hungary the political right-wing concentrates on cultural resentment and the political left-wing on party politics resentment. It raises questions about whether this distinction is also visible in far-left and far-right-wing pseudo-media. When it comes to discourse and emotions, it is also imperative to

study the effects of linguistic emotion ascriptions to political camps in journalistic media (who is allegedly experiencing which

emotions?). Different emotion ascriptions (which may or may not accurately represent existing collective and group-based emotions) do lead to different reactive emotions toward political groups (Wunderlich et al. 2022).

Further research should also explore the characteristics of the individuals fueling this resentment. This approach is dual as it considers individual and collective behaviors. Individual behaviors are composed of both top-down and bottom-up perspectives. The former includes leaders who might capitalize on the population's grievances (Capelos, Nield and Salmela 2023), but who also use emotional frames to provoke trust in their leadership capacities during a crisis (Palau-Sampio and Carratalá 2022). The current studies on emotions and political discourse focus on a specific category of leaders (Prime Ministers and Presidents) which have definite audiences (Palau-Sampio and Carratalá 2022). Given the increasing fragmentation of audiences, other types of discourse should be explored, such as the ones given by an institutional body, young and female leaders. On the other hand, the bottom-up perspectives focus on individual characteristics (Erdoğan and Semerci 2020). Nonetheless, individual and collective behaviors are interrelated, and future research should also compare individual and collective affective experiences (Capelos and Chrona 2018).

Emotion Sensitive Democratic Listening and Civil Society Actors

Scientific analysis should be much more nuanced than the kind of analysis that we are all exposed to on social media platforms. In this kind of scientific analysis, one should be able to see the objective elaboration of all the inputs coming from different stakeholders involved in the complex social, economic, and political processes. Listening to the voices of the members of civil society is an important task that the PLEDGE team adheres to.

As Celis and Childs (2024) rightfully state traditional representation theory assumes that elected representatives know the interests of the represented and act on them. In practice, the ways in which elected representatives come to know the interests of those they represent, and how interest aggregation takes place, are not always obvious or agreed upon (Disch 2021). We contend that the represented, and especially those who have been historically under- or misrepresented, are liable to experience unfair consideration of their interests in the absence of democratic listening. The effect of this is to risk the reproduction of their poverty of political representation, a situation only exacerbated in contemporary politics characterized by inequality, diversity, and polarization (Celis and Childs 2024). Theories and practices of representation thus need to take democratic listening much more seriously. Active listening involves attentiveness, awareness, consideration, mindfulness, and observance (Celis and Childs 2024).

PLEDGE embraces a democratic design approach to create emotion-sensitive frameworks for democratic processes (Legein et al. 2024). As our colleagues involved in the WP6 specialized in Democratic Innovations and Interventions put forward these designs challenge the traditional view that emotions are disruptive and should be excluded from policy-making and decision-making. Instead, they recognize emotions as integral to political actors, influencing their behavior and motivation to engage in and sustain participation in democratic processes. Emotion-sensitive democratic designs aim to implement practices that cultivate and nurture pro-democratic emotions and mechanisms while addressing and mitigating anti-democratic emotions to support a healthier democratic environment (Legein et al. 2024).

(DemSoc) in Barcelona on 27 September 2024, at the Canodrom venue (Barcelona), with the Participation of a diverse group of professionals working in areas such as technopolitics, urban planning, democratic innovation, and community participation, PLEDGE team tested a democratic design to conduct an experience of democratic listening. The workshop aimed to explore how emotions influence democratic processes and how they can be channeled through democratic design.

The participants made it very clear in their narratives that emotions are central to political dynamics, influencing perceptions of political elite and decision makers. Negative emotions like fear, anger, and frustration often drive polarization, reducing constructive dialogue and increasing divisions. On the other hand, collective emotions based on shared grievances (e.g., economic injustice or exclusion) can mobilize movements for change (e.g., "Indignados" in Spain, Occupy Wall Street in New York) (see also Salmela and von Scheve, 2018; Gerbaudo, 2017).

Our interlocutors also made it very clear that if ignored, grievances can escalate into radicalization, threatening democratic stability. It was also made clear in the workshop that shared grievances can drive political mobilization but also risk fueling extremism if unaddressed. To that effect, the participants addressed that democratic institutions must acknowledge and respond to grievances to prevent alienation and ensure stability.

Emotions can also be perceived by the political elite and decision-makers as positive channels for active participation in deliberative democratic processes. The participants made clear in the workshop that emotional empowerment through hope, pride, and a sense of community can strengthen engagement in democracy. In that sense, our interlocutors suggested that all kinds of institutions and decision-makers should channel emotions constructively by creating participatory spaces like citizen assemblies, mini-public forums, and participatory budgeting, fostering trust and involvement. Democratic design can offer a framework for inclusive governance in which emotions are not seen as obstacles but essential elements of democracy. Properly managed, they can foster participation, bridge divides, and drive systemic improvements through democratic design.

2.5 Policy Implications from Recent Scholarship

Exploring ways to address the root causes of populism and emotional politics in economic insecurity, social dislocation and marginalization that makes people more open to political entrepreneurs mobilizing political support through anti-social emotional appeals, narratives and practices should always remain a priority, along with other strategies and measures (Kaya 2019). Many of the EU-funded projects (including BRaVE, cohSMO, ISLAMOPHOBISM and others) have already highlighted the need for enhancing measures of social integration, countering social exclusion and empowering local communities and voluntary sector organizations. This would require a partnership between different levels of state authorities as well as the inclusion of civil society, educational organizations and community members themselves.

One alternative, policy-relevant way of looking at grievance politics is through the relationship between representatives and represented. Grievances take root in the poverty of the representative relationships, particularly

regarding feminist representation (Celis and Childs 2020; Celis and Childs 2023; Ingelgom, Amara-Hammou and Celis forthcoming). The feminist approach to representative relationships provides solutions through group advocacy, account giving and democratic listening. These concepts, based on the principles of inclusiveness, responsiveness and egalitarianism, fulfill the need for accountability at the foundation of representation (Celis and Childs 2023; Celis and Childs forthcoming).

Enhancing the relationship between the representatives and those whom they represent is also essential when facing a global crisis. A better understanding of emotions and grievances in politics would enable leaders to develop arguments to persuade individuals with high and low RWA and SDO. These narratives, using emotions for pro-democratic communication strategies, would represent an efficient tool to counterattack conspiracy theories such as those exacerbating vaccine hesitancy during a pandemic (Bilewicz and Soral 2022). Although these implications are not limited to global health crises, the dynamics of the representative-represented relationship could differ in other complex moments, for instance, terrorist attacks. This highlights the necessity to consider emotional and rational frames of leadership discourses in various contexts.

Finding tools for effective communication strategies by moving away from negative associations in emotional politics (i.e. “angry men”, “nasty women”, “extremist youth”, “impulsive youth”, “irrational”, “unpredictable”, “radical”) and finding alternative symbolic instruments and words to harness emotional politics in a pro-social way is a third important priority. We need to think about converters to transform anti-democratic expressions of grievance into pro-democratic expressions.

3. Conclusions

3.1. Summary of the key findings and results of the deliverable

The First Needs Analysis Report provided an overview of the interdisciplinary scholarship that has been produced over the last few years on the issues of grievance-driven, emotional politics. This sphere of research has been developing with increasing intensity and conceptual, analytical and methodological innovation. Taking stock of the existing research, understanding its key findings, identifying scholarly trends, and emerging methodological and empirical challenges as well as breakthroughs is a necessary first step for undertaking a large new research project that responds to similar research and policy problems.

The report brought to light a variety of perspectives on emotional politics along with specific empirical trends and research preferences revealing the directions for future research. Specifically, the report identified the need to consider a wider range of emotions, and consider interrelations, loops and emotional clusters, emotional mechanisms and interactions with ideas, values and identities. Given a diverse set of conceptual tools, the report revealed the need for developing a more integrated and coherent set of concepts, their operationalizations and approaches that could be translated across different countries and contexts, and used for coordinated data gathering that can be employed for responding to a wide variety of research questions from different disciplines.

The PLEDGE consortium members have already analysed policy design practices aimed at addressing the emotional economy of grievances (Capelos et al. 2016; Kinnvall, Manners and Mitzen 2020; Celis and Childs 2020, 2023), using interpretive policy analysis of values, identities, and emotions. PLEDGE members have also studied affective multi-level policy processes on European themes and seen how crises are communicated and negotiated with citizens (Palonen 2011; Koljonen and Palonen 2021). There is over a decade of practical experience in participatory designing, implementing and evaluating democratic innovation at different levels of governance (Kuokkanen and Palonen 2018). The PLEDGE project's key imperative at this moment is the development of an integrated conceptual and analytical framework that would enable a more coordinated data collection that could be used across different research teams and speak to the variety of research questions posed by consortium members to develop a more advanced understanding as well as practices and tools for promoting emotionally responsive democratic governance and political communication, and foster pro-democratic forms of civic engagement.

3.2 Limitations of the deliverable

The PLEDGE First Needs Analysis is inherently limited by the dynamic and evolving nature of emotional and political contexts. As PLEDGE data and literature continue to be composed, collected, categorized, and analyzed, ongoing refinements are anticipated. The theory of emotional mechanisms, still in its nascent and developing stages, invites an expanded engagement with relevant scholarly domains,

including the sociology of emotions, political psychology, and participatory action research that bridges academic and practical expertise. Furthermore, the project aims to advance its understanding of emotionally responsive democratic design and governance, with iterative testing planned across various contexts in subsequent phases of the PLEDGE initiative. Consequently, the First Needs Analysis is regarded as a provisional framework, necessitating continuous updates to incorporate emerging research and insights derived from evolving democratic design practices.

3.3. Recommendations for future actions

PLEDGE project promotes democratic designs that bring together all the stakeholders in mini-public forums, citizenship assemblies, spaces of encounter, and third spaces where the acts of democratic listening take place. Active listening is essential to address the interests of underrepresented groups and break cycles of poor political representation. PLEDGE members also underscore that emotions, both positive (hope, pride) and negative (fear, frustration), are central to political behavior. Properly managed, they can empower citizens and strengthen democracy. We also claim that shared grievances can drive political change but, if ignored, risk escalating into radicalization. Institutions must address them to ensure stability. Democratic designs that embrace emotions foster inclusion, bridge divides, and improve participation through tools like citizen assemblies.

4. Bibliography

Albertson, B., & Gadarian, S. K. (2012). Who's afraid of immigration?. In G. Freeman, et al. (Eds.), *Immigration and public opinion* (pp. 140-156). Routledge.

Arzheimer, K. (2009). Contextual factors and the extreme right vote in Western Europe, 1980–2002. *American Journal of Political Science*, 53 (2), 259–275.

Bakker, B. N., Rooduijn, M., & Schumacher, G. (2016). The psychological roots of populist voting. *European Journal of Political Research*, 55, 302–320.

Bilewicz, M. (2022). Conspiracy beliefs as an adaptation to historical trauma. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 53, 80–85.

Bilewicz, M., & Liu, J. H. (2020). Collective victimhood as a form of adaptation: A world-systems perspective. In J. R. Vollhardt (Ed.), *The social psychology of collective victimhood* (pp. 120–140). Oxford University Press.

Bock, P. (2018), *Community: The Structure of Belonging*, Oakland (CA): Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

Brader, T. (2006). *Campaigning for Hearts and Minds: How Emotional Appeals in Political Ads Work*. University of Chicago Press.

Calvillo, D. P., et al. (2020). Political ideology predicts perceptions of the threat of COVID-19 (and susceptibility to fake news about it). *Social Psychological and Personality Science* 11.8: 1119-1128.

Capelos, T., & Demertzis, T. (2022). Sour grapes: Ressentiment as the affective response of grievance politics. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 35(1), 107-129.

Capelos, T., Exadaktylos, T., Chrona, S., & Pouloupoulou, M. (2018). The emotional economy of the European financial crisis in the UK press. *International Journal of Communication*, 12, 2088-2113.

Capelos, T., Salmela, M. & Krisciunaite, G. (2022). Grievance Politics: An Empirical Analysis of Anger through the Emotional Mechanism of Ressentiment. *Politics and Governance*, 10(4), 384-395.

Capelos, Tereza, et al. (2024). The Anti-Social Triad of Grievance Politics: An integrated model of reactionism, resentment, and collective narcissism. *American Behavioral Scientist*. DOI: 10.1177/00027642241240351

Capelos, T., Nield, E., and Salmela, M. (2023). Narratives of success and failure in resentment: Assuming victimhood and transmuting frustration among young Korean men. *Social sciences* 12.5: 259.

Celis, K. and Childs, S. (2024). Performing Democratic Listening, in P. Diehl and M. Saward (eds.), *Bodies, Spaces, Claims*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. DOI: 10.1093/oso/9780198934905.003.0007

Celis, K. and Childs, S. (2020). *Feminist Democratic Representation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Celis, K., & Childs, S. (2023). From women's presence to feminist representation: second-generation design for women's group representation. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 10(1), 97-117.

Celis, K., Knops, L., Van Ingelgom, V., & Verhaegen, S. (2021). Resentment and coping with the democratic dilemma. *Politics and Governance*, 9(3), 237–247.

Cooley, C. (1902). *Human Nature and Conduct*. New York: Scribners, 413.

Cramer, K. J. (2016). *The Politics of Resentment: Rural Consciousness in Wisconsin and the Rise of Scott Walker*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Demertzis, N. (2006). Emotions and Populism. In S. Clarke, P. Hoggett, & S. Thompson (Eds.), *Emotion, Politics and Society* (pp. 112-126). Palgrave Macmillan.

Disch, L. (2021). *Making Constituencies: Representation as Mobilization in Mass Democracy*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.

Elias, N. (1998). *Civilisation, Power and Knowledge: Selected Writings*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Erçetin, T. and Erdoğan, E. (2021). Mirror, mirror on the wall, please tell me...': the populist rhetoric of the 'new' media of 'new Turkey' during the April 16, 2017 referendum. *Turkish Studies*, 22(2), 290-313.

Erdoğan, E., and Uyan-Semerci, P. (2020). Scapegoats to be "Served Hot": local perceptions about Syrians in a fragile context. *Journal of Conflict Transformation & Security*, 8(1), 28-54.

Erisen, C., et al. (2021). Psychological correlates of populist attitudes. *Political Psychology* 42: 149-171.

Diefenbach, A., and von Scheve, C. (2022). 'Islamisation of the Occident': fear of Islam as a mobilising force of the European new right. *Emotions and Society*, ePub ahead of print. DOI:10.1332/263169021X16432482503480

Gerbaudo, P. (2017) The indignant citizen: anti-austerity movements in southern Europe and the anti-oligarchic reclaiming of citizenship, *Social Movement Studies*, 16:1, 36-50, DOI: 10.1080/14742837.2016.1194749

result. *The Political Quarterly* 87.3: 323-332.

Guilluy, C. (2018). *No Society. La Fin de la Classe Moyenne Occidentale*. Paris: Flammarion.

Esses, V. M., Hamilton, L. K., & Gaucher, D. (2017). The global refugee crisis: Empirical evidence and policy implications for improving public attitudes and facilitating refugee resettlement. *Social Issues and Policy Review*, 11, 78-123.

Fischer, F. (2010). Policy deliberation: Confronting subjectivity and emotional expression. *Critical Policy Studies*, 3(3-4), 407-420.

Gest, J., Reny, T., and Mayer, J. (2018). Roots of the radical right: Nostalgic deprivation in the United States and Britain. *Comparative Political Studies* 51.13: 1694-1719.

Golder, M. (2016). Far right parties in Europe. *Annual review of political science* 19, 477- 497.

Goodwin, D. K. (2019). *Leadership: In turbulent times*. Simon & Schuster.

Hirvonen, O., and Pennanen, J. (2019). Populism as a pathological form of politics of recognition. *European Journal of Social Theory* 22.1: 27-44.

Honneth, A. (1996). *The struggle for recognition: The moral grammar of social conflicts* (J. Anderson, Trans.). Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.

Horner, R., Schindler, S., Haberly, D., & Aoyama, Y. (2018). Globalisation, uneven development and the North–South ‘big switch’. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 11 (1), 17–33.

Huber, Robert A., et al. (2021). Is populism a challenge to European energy and climate policy? Empirical evidence across varieties of populism. *Journal of European Public Policy* 28.7: 998-1017.

Huddy, L., Feldman, S., & Cassese, E. (2008). On the distinct political effects of anxiety and anger. In W. R. Neuman, G. E. Marcus, M. MacKuen, & A. N. Crigler (Eds.), *The affect effect* (pp. 202–230). University of Chicago Press.

Huntington, S. (1996). *The Clash of Civilisations and the Remaking of the World Order*. New York: Simon & Schuster.

Hutchison, E. & Bleiker, R. (2014). Theorizing emotions in world politics. *International Theory*, 6(3), 491-514.

Inglehart, R., & Norris, P. (2019). *Cultural backlash: Trump, Brexit, and Authoritarian Populism*. Cambridge University Press.

Illouz, E. (2023). *The emotional life of populism: How fear, disgust, resentment, and love undermine democracy*. John Wiley & Sons.

Iyengar, S., et al. (2019). *The origins and consequences of affective*

polarization in the United States. *Annual review of political science*, 22, 129-146.

Jesuit, D. K., Paradowski, P. R., & Mahler, V. A. (2009). Electoral Support for Extreme Right-Wing Parties: A Sub-National Analysis of Western European Elections. *Electoral Studies*, 28(2), 279–290.

Jost, J. T., Sterling, J., & Stern, C. (2017). Getting closure on conservatism, or the politics of epistemic and existential motivation. In L. J. Shrum, A. Kruglanski, & T. F. Pettigrew (Eds.), *The Motivation-Cognition Interface: From the Lab to the Real World: A Festschrift in Honor of Arie W. Kruglanski* (pp. 56-87). Taylor & Francis.

Kaya, A. (2019). *Populism and heritage in Europe: Lost in diversity and unity*. Routledge.

Kaya, A. (2021). Islamist and Nativist Reactionary Radicalisation in Europe. *Politics and Governance*, 9(3), 204–214.

Kaya, A., Adam-Troian, J., & Tecmen, A. (2021). Youth Extremism as a Response to Global Threats? A Threat-Regulation Perspective on Violent Extremism Among the Youth. *European Psychologist*, 26(1), 15-28.

Kaya, A. and Kayaoğlu, A. (2017). Islamophobia in the EU 15: A Quantitative Analysis, *Uluslararası İlişkiler Dergisi*, 14 (53), 45-68.

Kazlauskaitė, R. (2022a). Embodying resentmentful victimhood: Virtual reality re-enactment of the Warsaw uprising in the Second World War Museum in Gdańsk. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 28(6), 699-713.

Kazlauskaitė, R. (2022b). Key Concept: Virtual Reality History. In S. Berger, B. Bevernage, M. Grever, O. E. Williams, Q. E. Wang, & T. Loughran (Eds.), *Bloomsbury History: Theory and Method*.

Kazlauskaitė, R., & Salmela, M. (2022). Mediated emotions: Shame and pride in Polish right-wing media coverage of the 2019 European Parliament elections. *Innovation*, 35(1), 130-149.

Kimmel, M. S. (2003). Globalisation and its Mal(e)contents: The Gendered Moral and Political Economy of Terrorism, *International Sociology*, 18 (3); , 603–620.

Kinnvall, C. (2019). Populism, ontological insecurity and Hindutva: Modi and the masculinization of Indian politics. *Cambridge Rev. of Int. Affairs*, 32(3), 283-302.

Kinnvall, C., & Singh, A. (2022). Enforcing and Resisting Hindutva: Popular Culture, the COVID-19 Crisis and Fantasy Narratives of Motherhood and Pseudoscience in India. *Social Sciences*, 11(12), 550.

Kinnvall, C., & Svensson, T. (2022). Exploring the populist 'mind': Anxiety, fantasy and everyday populism. *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 24(3), 1-17.

Kiss, B. (2021). Double resentment: The political communication of Kulturkampf in Hungary. *Politics and Governance*, 9(3), 227-236.

Knops, L. (2023). The Fear we Feel Everyday: Affective Temporalities in Fridays for Future. *South Atlantic Quarterly*, 122(1).

Knops, L., Mercenier, H., Randour, F., Van Ingelgom, V., & Celis, K. (Eds.). (2023). *Bitter-Sweet Democracy? Exploring citizens' resentment towards politics*. Open Book Publishers.

Koljonen, J. M., & Palonen, E. (2021). Performing and contesting control during of the Covid-19 pandemic in Finland: interpretative topic modelling and discourse theoretical reading of the government communication and hashtag landscape. *Frontiers in Political Science*.

Kösen, M. G., and Erdoğan, E. (2023). 'Now we are whole:' humiliation, shame and pride in Aliyev's discourse on the 2020 Nagorno-Karabakh War. *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies*, 1-18.

Köttig, M., Bitzan, M. and Petö, A. (Eds.) (2017). *Gender and Far Right Politics in Europe*. London: Palgrave.

Kuokkanen, K. & Palonen, E. (2018). Urban Participatory Projects in Helsinki. In S. Knierbein & T. Viderman (Eds.), *Public space unbound: Urban emancipation and the post-political condition* (pp. 99-112). Routledge.

Laclau, E., and Mouffe, C. (2014). *Hegemony and socialist strategy: Towards a radical democratic politics*. Vol. 8. Verso Books.

Landwehr, C. (2022). Contested Representation: Populist Challenges, Political Support and the Reform of Democratic Institutions. In C. Landwehr, T. Saalfeld, & A. Schäfer (Eds.), *Contested Representation: Challenges, Shortcomings and Reforms* (pp. 15-31). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Legein, T., Celis, K., Nagy, Z., & Di Siena, D. (2024). "Report on Design Principles for Emotion Sensitive Policy Making," *PLEDGE Wp6 Report*, PLEDGE Project

Lipiński, A., & Szabo, G. (2023). Heroisation and victimisation: Populism, commemorative narratives and National Days in Hungary and Poland. *Journal of Contemporary European Studies*. Advance online publication.

Manners, I. (2014). Political Psychology of European Integration. In P. Nesbitt-Larking, C.

Medvedev, S. (2024). *A war made in Russia*. John Wiley & Sons.

Kinnvall, C., Capelos, T. & Dekker, H. (Eds.) (2014). *The Palgrave Handbook of Global Political Psychology* (pp. 263–278). Palgrave Macmillan.

- uniquely social roots of Trump support. *American Pol. Science Review*, 115(4), 1508–1516.
- Mayer, S. J., & Nguyen, C. (2021). Angry Reactionary Narcissists? Anger Activates the Link Between Narcissism and Right-Populist Party Support. *Politics and Governance*, 9(3), 248-259.
- Moffitt B. and S. Thorney (2014). Rethinking Populism: Politics, Mediatisation and Political Style. *Political Studies*, 62 (2), 381-397
- Morrell, M. (2013). *Empathy and Democracy: Feeling, Thinking, and Deliberation*. Penn State University Press.
- Mozolevska, Alina (2024). Unveiling the War and Constructing Identities: Exploring Memes in Ukrainian and Russian Social Media during the Russian Invasion of Ukraine. *Czech Journal of International Relations*.
- Nguyen, C., Salmela, M., & von Scheve, C. (2021). From specific worries to generalized anger. In M. Oswald (Ed.), *Palgrave Handbook of Populism* (pp. 145-160). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Palau-Sampio, D. (2022). Pseudo-Media Disinformation Patterns: Polarised Discourse, Clickbait and Twisted Journalistic Mimicry. *Journalism Practice*.
- Palonen, E. (2011). Multi-level cultural policy and politics of European Capitals of Culture. *Nordisk kulturpolitisk tidsskrift*, 13(1), 87-108.
- Palonen, E. (2018). Performing the nation: the Janus-faced populist foundations of illiberalism in Hungary. *J. of Contemporary European Studies*, 26(3), 308-321.
- Petersen, R. (2017). "Emotions as the residue of lived experience." *PS: Political Science & Politics* 50.4: 932-935.
- Pontusson, J., and Weisstanner, D. (2018). Macroeconomic conditions, inequality shocks and the politics of redistribution, 1990–2013. *Journal of European Public Policy*. VOL. 25, NO. 1, 31–58, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2017.1310280>
- Pyszczyński, T., Rothschild, Z., and Abdollahi, A. (2008). Terrorism, violence, and hope for peace: A terror management perspective, *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 17 (5), 318–322.
- Roberts, K. M. (2006). Populism, Political Conflict, and Grass-Roots Organization in Latin America, *Comparative Politics*, 38 (2), 127–48.
- Rodrigues-Pose, A. (2018). The revenge of the places that don't matter (and what to do about it), *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 11, 189–209.
- Rothstein, B. (2012). Good Governance. In D. Levi-Faur (Ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Governance* (Online ed., pp. 1-18). Oxford Academic.
- Rydgren, J., and Ruth, P. (2013). Contextual Explanations of

Radical Right-Wing Support in Sweden: Socioeconomic Marginalization, Group Threat, and the Halo Effect. *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 36: 711–28. DOI: [10.1080/01419870.2011.623786](https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2011.623786).

Salojärvi, V., Palonen, E., Horsmanheimo, L., and Kylli, R. M. (2023). Protecting the future ‘Us’: a rhetoric-performative multimodal analysis of the polarising far-right YouTube campaign videos in Finland. *Visual Studies*, 38(5), 851-866. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1472586X.2023.2249430>

Salice, A., & Salmela, M. (2022). What are Emotional Mechanisms? *Emotions and Society*, 4(1), 49-68.

Salmela, M., & Capelos, T. (2021). Resentment: A Complex Emotion or an Emotional Mechanism of Psychic Defenses. *Pol. & Govern.*, 9(3), 191–203.

Salmela, M., & Szanto, T. (2024). Two Types of Political Resentment. Manuscript submitted for publication. In M. Lewis, & A. Kauppinen (Eds.), *The Moral Psychology of Resentment* Rowman & Littlefield Publishers .

Salmela, M., & von Scheve, C. (2017). Emotional roots of right-wing political populism. *Social Science Information*, 56(4), 567–595.

Salmela, M., & von Scheve, C. (2018). Emotional Dynamics of Right- and Left-wing Political Populism. *Humanity & Society*, 42(4), 434–454.

Sanders, E. B.-N., & Stappers, P. J. (2008). Co-creation and the new landscapes of design. *CoDesign*, 4(1), 5–18.

Scharfbillig, M., Smillie, L., Mair, D., Sienkiewicz, M., Keimer, J., Pinho dos Santos, R., Vinagreiro Alves, H., Vecchione, E. & Scheunemann, L. (2021). Values and Identities - a policymaker’s guide. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

Schuler, D., & Namioka, A. (Eds.). (1993). *Participatory design: Principles and practices*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.

Sharafutdinova, G. (2020). *The red mirror: Putin’s leadership and Russia’s insecure identity*. Oxford University Press.

Stavrakakis, Y. (2017). Discourse theory in populism research: Three challenges and a dilemma. *Journal of language and politics*, 16(4), 523-534.

Stockemer, D., Lentz, T., and Mayer, D. (2018). Individual Predictors of the Radical Right-Wing Vote in Europe: A Meta-Analysis of Articles in Peer-Reviewed Journals (1995–2016). *Government and Opposition* 53: 569–93. DOI: [10.1017/gov.2018.2](https://doi.org/10.1017/gov.2018.2).

Sullivan, G. B. (2021). Political reactionism as affective practice: UKIP supporters and non-voters in pre-Brexit England. *Pol. & Govern.*, 9(3), 260-273.

Is yearning for the past successful on social media? *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 35(1), 150-171.

Szabó, Lilla Petronella, and Szabó, G. (2022). Attack of the critics: Metaphorical delegitimation in Viktor Orbán's discourse during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Language and Politics* 21.2: 255-276.

Szebeni, Z., and Salojärvi, V. (2022). "Authentically" Maintaining Populism in Hungary—Visual Analysis of Prime Minister Viktor Orbán's Instagram. *Mass Communication and Society*, 25(6), 812-837. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15205436.2022.2111265>

Vlandas, T., and Halikiopoulou, D. (2019). Does Unemployment Matter? Economic Insecurity, Labour Market Policies and the Far-Right Vote in Europe. *European Political Science* 18 (2019): 421–38. DOI: [10.1057/s41304-018-0161-z](https://doi.org/10.1057/s41304-018-0161-z).

Weyland, K. (2001). Clarifying a contested concept: Populism in the study of Latin American politics. *Comparative politics*: 1-22.

Wunderlich, P., Nguyen, C., & von Scheve, C. (2023). Angry populists or concerned citizens? How linguistic emotion ascriptions shape affective, cognitive, and behavioural responses to political outgroups. *Cognition and Emotion*, 37(1), 147–161.

Zürn, M. (2022). How Non-Majoritarian Institutions Make Silent Majorities Vocal: A Political Explanation of Authoritarian Populism. *Perspectives on Politics*, 20(3), 788-807.

